

Antifungal susceptibility profile and molecular epidemiology of recurrent vulvovaginal candidiasis in Yasuj, southwestern Iran

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Summary

Candidal vaginitis is a common infection causing various clinical presentations that can also emerge as recurrent vulvovaginal candidiasis (RVVC) in many patients. *Candida albicans* is the most common causative agent of RVVC. Since there is no definitive guideline for RVVC

treatment, it is important to consider the species and susceptibility profile of the isolate to use the appropriate antifungals. The present study was conducted to determine the prevalence of RVVC, the etiological agents, and their antifungal susceptibility among clinically suspected patients in the Yasuj region, southwest Iran. The isolated yeasts were identified based on the morphological and molecular methods followed by antifungal susceptibility testing. Overall, 65 *Candida* strains were isolated from RVVC samples. *Candida albicans* (95.4%) were the main causative agents, followed by *C. glabrata* (3.1%), and *C. krusei* (1.53%). According to our findings, 20.7% and 22.4% of *Candida* isolates were resistant to fluconazole (MIC \geq 8 μ g/mL) and clotrimazole (MIC \geq 1 μ g/mL), respectively. Although *C. albicans* was still the main causative agent of RVVC incidence, the importance of accurate identification of *Candida* strains and determination of antifungal susceptibility are emphasized. Moreover, in this study, low drug-resistance was found among isolated *Candida* species in Yasuj.

Key words

Recurrent vulvovaginal candidiasis, antifungal susceptibility, fluconazole, clotrimazole

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Introduction

Candidal vulvovaginitis is a common infection among women of reproductive ages.¹ Clinical symptoms including irritation, soreness, dyspareunia, and vaginal discharge.² The infection can emerge recurrently in approximately 5% of patients with vulvovaginal candidiasis (VVC).³ Recurrent VVC (RVVC) is defined as four or more episodes of symptomatic acute *Candida* vaginitis in 12 months.⁴ There are many host factors associated with RVVC, including diabetes mellitus, aging, changes in estrogen hormone levels due to oral contraceptive pills and hormone therapy, use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, autoimmune and immunosuppressive conditions such as AIDS, lupus erythematosus, and corticosteroid therapy.^{5,6} Several species of *Candida* are associated with RVVC; however, *Candida albicans* is the most common causative agent.⁴ In the last decade, *non-albicans* species have emerged as causative agents of RVVC⁷ among which *C. glabrata* and *C. tropicalis* were more frequent. Studies have

shown that geographical differences may affect the prevalence of *Candida* species isolated from RVVC.⁸

Although varied responses have been reported for the treatment of RVVC with topical and systemic drugs,⁹ there is no definitive cure for RVVC. The most convenient antifungal drugs for RVVC therapy are oral triazole drugs (i.e., fluconazole and itraconazole) and topical drugs (i.e., clotrimazole, miconazole, and nystatin).² However, incomplete treatments and prolonged prophylaxis with antifungal drugs have made it difficult to treat RVVC.¹⁰ Therefore, the treatment of such patients should be based on a combination of results achieved from antifungal susceptibility tests compared with previous treatment.¹¹ The identification of *Candida* strains causing RVVC is important to determine the susceptibility to antifungal drugs in symptomatic RVVC. In this regard, to identify these fungi, the focus has shifted toward molecular strategies that are more accurate and less susceptible to variations accounting for growth conditions and phenotypic switching.¹²

The present study aimed to determine the frequency of *Candida* species in RVVC women referred to two gynecology clinics in Yasuj city in the southwest of Iran. Besides, the *in vitro* antifungal susceptibility profile of the clinical *Candida* isolates was evaluated against fluconazole (FLC), nystatin (NYS), and clotrimazole (CLO).

Materials and Methods

Sampling and isolation of *Candida* species

A total of 100 vaginal clinical specimens were collected from females suspected of RVVC referring to the Department of Gynecology of Shahid-Mofatteh Clinic and Department of obstetrics of a private midwifery clinic, Yasuj, Iran, from November 2017 to November 2018. Each specimen was taken with sterile cotton swabs from the lateral wall of the patient's vagina. The samples were cultured on Sabouraud dextrose agar with 50 mg/L Chloramphenicol (Quelab Inc., Canada). All cultures were incubated at 37°C for 48h. The isolated yeast colonies were sub-cultured on CHROMagar (CHROMagar™, Rambach™, AquaCHROM™) media for phenotypic identification.

Molecular identification

The extraction of DNA was carried out using the boiling method.¹³ In this regard, a portion of a colony was transferred to sterile microtubes containing 100 µl sterile distilled water and placed in boiling water for 20 min. Subsequently, the suspensions containing DNA were centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 10 min, and the supernatants were separated as the crude DNA and used for polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification. The primers ITS1 [5'-TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG-3'] and ITS4 [5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3'] were used for PCR amplification of the entire internal transcribed spacer 1 and 2 at the ribosomal DNA gene. The PCR products were subjected to 1.5% agarose gel electrophoresis, visualized by staining with ethidium bromide (0.5 mg/L), and photographed under ultraviolet light. Subsequently, the PCR products underwent digestion with the restriction enzyme *MspI* (Fermentas, Lithuania) for restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) analysis.^{14,15} To achieve precise strain discriminatory patterns, PCR products were digested in a 15 µL of a final reaction volume, containing 8 µL of PCR product, 0.5 µL of *MspI* enzyme, 1 µL of digesting buffer, and 6.5 µL of deionized distilled water, at 37°C for 2 h. The restriction fragment was separated on 2% agarose gel in Tris/Borate/EDTA buffer. Finally, the species were identified according to the size of DNA fragments in comparison with the already published data.

Antifungal susceptibility testing

Antifungal susceptibility testing was performed according to the recommendations proposed by the M27-A3 and M27-S4 documents of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI).^{16,17} Out of 65 *Candida* isolates, 58 isolates were evaluated for *in vitro* antifungal susceptibility against FLC, CLO, and NYS (Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA). During the storage and processing, seven isolates were missed. The remaining isolates were sub-cultured on SDA plates and incubated at 35°C for 24-48 h. The ranges of tested drug dilution were 0.063–64 mg/L for FLC and NYS and 0.016–16mg/L for CLO. *C. parapsilosis* ATCC 22019 was used as a quality control strain. Homogeneous conidial suspensions were spectrophotometrically measured at the 530 nm wavelength to a percent transmission within the range of 75-77%. The final inoculum suspensions were adjusted to 0.5-2.5 x 10³ conidia/mL in RPMI-1640 with L-glutamine and without sodium bicarbonate (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) buffered at pH 7.0 with 0.165 M 3-(N-Morpholino) propanesulfonic acid acid (MOPS, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). The 96-well microplates were incubated at 35°C and examined visually after 24 and 48 h to determine minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values according to the recommendations proposed by the CLSI M27-A3 and M27-S4 documents.^{16,17} Subsequently, the geometric means (GM) of MICs, MIC₅₀, MIC₉₀, and MIC ranges were calculated. The interpretation of MICs (i.e., susceptible, intermediate, and resistant) for FLC were made according to *Candida* species breakpoints defined in CLSI M27-S4.¹⁸ Since there is no established breakpoint for CLO, the researchers of current used a defined breakpoint published by Pelletier et al.¹⁹

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics were shown by frequency and percentage, and the analytical comparison was performed using the tests.

Results and Discussion

In this study, a total of 65 *Candida* strains were isolated from 100 patients with RVVC symptoms. The frequencies of isolates by age group were shown in Table 1. The age groups with most strains isolated were the 20-29 (41.5%)- and 30-39 (41.5%) – years-old. Overall, the mean age of patients was 31 years. No difference was observed between suspected patients and patients with positive cultures ($P=0.43$) regarding the age groups. The majority of patients had at least one symptom of VVC, including vulvovaginal itching (98%), burning

Table 1 Distribution of *Candida* species and age groups of 65 patients with recurrent vulvo-vaginal candidiasis.

Species	Number of isolates by age group					
	10 - 19	20 - 29	30 - 39	40 - 49	50 - 59	Not recorded
<i>Candida albicans</i>	2	27	24	7	1	1
<i>Candida glabrata</i>			2			
<i>Candida krusei</i>			1			
Total (%)	2 (3)	27 (41.5)	27 (41.5)	7 (11)	1 (1.5)	1 (1.5)

Table 2 Geometric means of MIC, MIC ranges, MIC₅₀, and MIC₉₀ values obtained by antifungal susceptibility testing of 58 *Candida* isolates obtained from 58 recurrent vulvovaginal candidiasis patients.

Strains	Antifungals	MIC Distribution (mg/L)										GM (mg/L)	Range (mg/L)	MIC ₅₀ (mg/L)	MIC ₉₀ (mg/L)	R (%)
		32	16	8	4	2	1	0.5	0.25	0.125	0.0625					
<i>C. albicans</i> (n:55)	FLC	8		3	2	3		21	12	1	5	0.85	0.0625-32	0.5	32	11 (20)
	CLO							10	1	26	13	0.24	0.0625-1	0.25	1	10 (18.2)
	NYS							9	34	8	3	1	0.9	0.125-2	1	2
<i>C. glabrata</i> (n:2)	FLC							1	1							
	CLO							2								2 (100)
	NYS							2								
<i>C. krusei</i> (n:1)	FLC			1												
	CLO							1								1 (100)
	NYS					1										
Total (n:58)	FLC	8		4	2	3		22	13	1	5	0.86	0.0625-32	0.5	32	12 (20.7)
	CLO							13	1	26	13	0.26	0.0625-1	0.25	1	13 (22.4)
	NYS					10	36	8	3	1		0.92	0.125-2	1	2	—

MIC: Minimum inhibitory concentration, GM: Geometric mean, MIC₅₀: minimal concentration capable of inhibiting 50% of isolates, MIC₉₀: minimal concentration capable of inhibiting 90% of isolates, FLC: Fluconazole, NYS: Nystatin, CLO: clotrimazole, R: resistance.

(83%), pain (68%), vaginal discharge (93%), and erythema with inflammation (79%) for at least 3 months. Furthermore, most patients received antifungal therapy for VVC. The most frequent antifungal drugs prescribed in the previous course of vaginitis were oral FLC (69%), intravaginal CLO (52%), and NYS (6%).

According to the classical and molecular identification techniques, *C. albicans* was the most common species (n=62; 95.4%), followed by *C. glabrata* (n=2; 3.1%) and *C. krusei* (n=1; 1.53%) (Table 1). Among the patients, only one woman had a mixed positive culture (*C. albicans* and *C. glabrata*). The results of phenotypic identification (i.e., colony color on CHROMagar *Candida*) were confirmed with the PCR-RFLP method.

Table 2 summarizes the GM MIC, MIC ranges, MIC₅₀, and MIC₉₀ of three antifungal agents against 58 *Candida* strains (*C. albicans* n=55, *C. glabrata* n=2, and *C. krusei* n=1). The GM MICs across all isolates were as follows: CLO (GM:0.26 mg/L), FLC (GM:0.86 mg/L), and NYS (GM:0.92 mg/L). The MIC range for all isolates were: CLO: 0.0625-1 mg/L, FLC: 0.0625-32 mg/L, and NYS: 0.125-2 mg/L. The MIC₅₀ and MIC₉₀ for all *Candida* strains were as follows respectively: CLO:0.025 mg/L, 1 mg/L; FLC: 0.5 mg/L, 32 mg/L; and NYS:1 mg/L, 2 mg/L. According to the CLSI interpretive criteria, our results indicated that 20.7% and 22.4% of *Candida* isolates were resistant to FLC (MIC≥8 mg/L) and CLO (MIC≥1 mg/L), respectively. There are no de-

defined breakpoints for NYS. Furthermore, CLO resistance was observed among 18.2% of *C. albicans* and 100% of *C. glabrata* and *C. krusei* isolates.

Recurrent VVC affects up to 5% of premenopausal women and it is an increasing challenge in clinical practice. It is estimated that RVVC affects nearly 138 million women worldwide annually and about 500 million over their lifetimes.^{2,20} It has been reported that *C. albicans* is the most common causative agent of VVC, followed by *C. glabrata*, which is the most commonly reported 'non-*albicans*' species.^{2,20} In our study, 65% of suspected RVVC patients had a positive *Candida* culture, which was higher than the findings (14.16%) revealed in the study conducted by Richter et al. in the United States.²¹ This discrepancy in the rate of positive *Candida* culture from recurrent infection may be attributed to host conditions, such as an underlying disease, hormone therapy, history of antifungal therapy, and lifestyle.²¹ Our results showed that a high prevalence of RVVC was observed in the age group of 20-39 years. This result was in line with those of other studies in which a high rate of RVVC infection was reported in the 20-30-year age group.^{22,23}

In the present study, *C. albicans* was the most frequent species (95.4%) in RVVC samples, followed by *C. glabrata* (3.1%) and *C. krusei* (1.53%). Similarly, Richter et al. reported *C. albicans* as the main causative agent of vaginitis (70.8%).²¹ Also, agree with our finding in a study *C. glabrata* and *C. krusei* were reported as the common non-*albicans* agent of vaginitis.²⁴ *Candida glabrata* has been introduced as the second agent of vaginitis in different studies in the world.²⁵⁻²⁷ However, Bitew et al. different recovery rates were reported for NAC species. The results of the mentioned study demonstrated *C. krusei* as the dominant NAC species, followed by *C. dubliniensis*.²⁸ Generally, it seems that the increase of NAC species, isolated from patients complaining of genital tract infection naturally resistant to antifungal agents, is probably related to the widespread and inappropriate use of azole antifungals. Besides, one study reported that women with positive non-*albicans* cultures were more likely to have multiple visits to their physicians for VV complaints.²⁹ Hence, accurate identification of non-*albicans* species in vaginal specimens is necessary.

Some non-*C. albicans* species are resistant to antifungal drugs, especially the azole class, and which lead to failure in vaginitis therapy.³⁰ It has been demonstrated that antimycotic prophylaxis with FLC for long periods is effective in the prevention of *Candida* recurrent episodes.³¹ Although 91% of RVVC patients receiving FLC for 6 months were cured after the cessation of the therapy, the improvement rate was observed in only 43% of patients.³¹ Furthermore, in

recent years, FLC resistance has been reported in women with RVVC infection.³² It was also reported that almost all women diagnosed with FLC-resistant *C. albicans* had experienced previous exposure to FLC.³² The rates of azole drug resistance are variable, and they can be affected by the prescribing patterns of clinicians for both prophylaxis and treatment. It is important to recognize that the overuse of topical agents has had other adverse outcomes as well, such as edema and irritability of the skin.^{33,34} Over the past few years, several cases of women with RVVC have been reported that have not responded to FLC induction therapy.^{35,36} Since it is not possible to find one regimen fit for all patients, antifungal susceptibility surveillance investigations exert an increasingly essential role in pursuing the progress of antifungal resistance and beginning appropriate primary antifungal therapy. In the current study, our results showed that 100% of *C. krusei* and 20% of *C. albicans* isolates were resistant to FLC. Also, 100% of non-*albicans* species were resistant to CLO. In contrast to our findings, Arzeni et al. reported no FLC resistance among *Candida* strains isolated from vaginal samples.³⁷ Although Richter et al. reported that 15.2% of *C. glabrata* strains isolated from *Candida* vaginitis were resistant to FLC,²¹ in the present study, FLC was found to have low MICs value (MIC₉₀ 0.5 mg/L) against *C. glabrata* isolates. These results indicate that the difference in azole- resistance among *Candida* strains isolated from candidal vaginitis may be associated with the history of alternative antifungal therapy. Furthermore, the difference in results can be due to antifungal susceptibility test methods and geographical variety.

According to the findings of this study, NYS had a low GM MIC value (0.92 mg/L) with MICs value ranges from 0.125-2 mg/L against *Candida* isolates. Richter et al. showed an NYS MIC₉₀ value of 4 mg/L for *Candida* strains isolated from VVC.²¹ In our study, the history of prescription of NYS was reported only for four patients that were associated with the *in vitro* results of NYS. Additionally, Wang et al. reported excellent *in vitro* activity (<4% resistance) of NYS against *Candida* species isolated from vaginal samples.³⁸ In line with the findings of the study performed by Wang et al., our results showed low NYS GM MIC (0.92 mg/L) against *Candida* species.

Conclusion

In conclusion, *C. albicans* was the main causative agent recovered in RVVC patients. Furthermore, the current study described FLC-resistance in 20.7% of *Candida* strains isolated from RVVC.

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Author contribution

ShahinTaj Aramesh collected specimens from patients, Mohammad Amin Ghatee and Saham Ansari analyzed the data and revised the manuscript, Ali Mousavizadeh analyzed the data, Shahamat Tabansirat, Vahid Kazemi, and Leila Rajabi carried out the experiments, Maral Gharaghani analyzed the results and wrote the manuscript, and Sadegh Nouripour-Sisakht designed and supervised the project.

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Ethics statement

This study was approved by the ethics committee of Yasuj University of Medical Sciences (ethical no. IR.YUMS.REC.1396.77 and IR.YUMS.REC.1397.110).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Περίληψη

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Η καντιντιασική κολπίτιδα είναι μια συνηθισμένη λοίμωξη με διάφορες κλινικές εκδηλώσεις. Μεταξύ αυτών μπορεί να εμφανιστεί σε πολλούς ασθενείς ως υποτροπιάζουσα αιδοιοκολπική καντιντίαση (RVVC). Η *Candida albicans* είναι ο πιο συχνός αιτιολογικός παράγοντας της RVVC. Δεδομένου ότι δεν υπάρχουν οριστικές κατευθυντήριες οδηγίες για τη θεραπευτική αντιμετώπιση της RVVC, είναι σημαντικό, για τη χρήση των κατάλληλων αντιμυκητικών, να λαμβάνετε υπόψη το είδος και το προφίλ ευαισθησίας της απομονούμενης *Candida*. Η παρούσα μελέτη σκοπό είχε τον προσδιορισμό του επιπολασμού της RVVC, των αιτιολογικών παραγόντων και της αντιμυκητικής ευαισθησίας τους μεταξύ κλινικά ύποπτων ασθενών στην περιοχή Yasuj, στο νοτιοδυτικό Ιράν. Οι απομονωθέντες ζυμομύκητες ταυτοποιήθηκαν με βάση φαινοτυπικές και μοριακές μεθόδους και ακολούθησε έλεγχος ευαισθησίας στα αντιμυκητικά. Συνολικά, απομονώθηκαν 65 στελέχη *Candida* από δείγματα RVVC. Η *C. albicans* (95,4%) ήταν το συχνότερα απομονούμενο είδος, ακολουθούμενη από *C. glabrata* (3,1%) και *C. krusei* (1,53%). Σύμφωνα με τα ευρήματα της μελέτης, το 20,7% και το 22,4% των *Candida* παρουσίασαν αντοχή στη φλουκοναζόλη (MIC \geq 8 μ g/mL) και στην κλοτριμαζόλη (MIC \geq 1 μ g/mL). Αν και η *C. albicans* εξακολουθεί να είναι ο κύριος αιτιολογικός παράγοντας της RVVC, τονίζεται η σημασία της ακριβούς ταυτοποίησης των απομονούμενων ειδών *Candida* και του προσδιορισμού της ευαισθησίας στα αντιμυκητικά. Επιπλέον, στην παρούσα μελέτη, βρέθηκε χαμηλή αντοχή στα φάρμακα μεταξύ των απομονωμένων ειδών *Candida*.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

Υποτροπιάζουσα αιδοιοκολπική καντιντίαση, ευαισθησία στα αντιμυκητικά, φλουκοναζόλη, κλοτριμαζόλη

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